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Effects Of Peer Assisted Learning Strategies And Students Engagement On Academic Performance Among Senior Secondary Schools In Sokoto Metropolis, Sokoto State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effects of Peer Assisted Learning Strategies (PALS) and Student Engagement (SE) on the academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto Metropolis, Sokoto State, Nigeria. The research adopted a quasi-experimental design involving pre-test and post-test measures to examine the impact of these instructional strategies on student outcomes. Five null hypotheses were formulated and tested at a 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed a significant improvement in students' academic performance following exposure to both Peer Assisted Learning Strategies and Student Engagement strategies. However, while gender did not significantly influence academic outcomes under PALS, a significant gender difference was observed under the Student Engagement strategy, with male students performing slightly better. No significant difference was found in the academic performance of students taught using PALS compared to those taught using SE, suggesting both strategies are equally effective in enhancing learning outcomes.

Keywords: Peer Assisted Learning Strategies, Student Engagement, learning outcomes

INTRODUCTION

Education is a catalyst for national development without which no nation can experience significant economic growth. Not just education but a qualitative and sustainable education. Qualitative education requires effective teaching and learning strategies, resourceful as well as motivated manpower. The best way to learn and retain knowledge is to teach it to another. Students improve their understanding and commitment if they teach or explain the material to someone else, even if it is to a computer (Park & Kim, 2016). This psychological phenomenon is known as the protégé effect, which underpins the concept of peer-assisted learning, where students or peers engage in a two-way, bilateral learning program. Peer-assisted learning is an instructional strategy commonly used to supplement and support classroom education where students play the roles of mentors and mentees.

It is most often referred to as peer tutoring, where academic support is provided by students to struggling peers (Chan, 2016). Thus, this study used the terms interchangeably. In essence, peer tutoring is a learning environment where authority is not expended to instigate learning between students who learn together and from each other. This is based on the principle that by understanding the subject matter and communicating their ideas to one another they can learn from their peers. Consequently (Boud, 2019). Peer Assisted Learning (PAL) and its variants have operated in the UK as a system of student-to-student support since the early 1990's (Wallace, 2021).

Peer assisted learning operates most usually by using trained second- or third-year students ('PAL Leaders'), working alone or in pairs, to regularly supervise the learning of a small group of first year students. This group learning is usually classroom-based (the 'PAL session') and is designed to offer a range of benefits to an institution, its teaching teams and courses, and to those students involved with it (Capstick & Fleming, 2019). The emphasis in Peer Assisted Learning is on active discussion and cooperative learning within the framework of a partnership with the formal structures of the course. Although nomenclature and operational issues vary, the core idea of Peer Assisted Learning as peer led, cooperative study sessions supplementing traditional teaching has changed little since Peer Assisted Learning first came to the UK over a decade ago. At this time, the model from which Peer Assisted Learning and a range of other schemes derived was the North American scheme termed Supplemental Instruction. Since the inception of Peer Assisted Learning in the UK, there has been a proliferation of the paradigm, with Peer Assisted Learning or similar schemes now operating across the full spectrum of degree courses at around twenty institutions. Peer Assisted Learning has also adapted to suit local conditions (Wallace, 2021).

Statements of the Problem

Despite the investment in education, to meet up with the present challenge of the 21st century, Students' performance at SSCE had still been recorded very low in biology when compared with the number of enrolment of students over the years. The Chief Examiners report on Senior Secondary School Students achievement (2020) in Mathematics and English studies revealed that, the subject had both the highest enrolment relative to other subjects and recorded poor achievement in the senior school certificate examination (SSCE). Adeduran, (2021), Ajajun & Tayo (2022), observed that Nigerian Educational system is still confronted with poor academic performance. The Chief Examiners report opined that the prevailing teaching method does not allow active students participation of students in class lessons. Students only memorize and regurgitate facts and concepts. Researchers have confirmed and suggested some modes of instructions to improve learners' interest in English and Mathematics. However, there persists learners' lack of interest in English and Mathematics across the globe, most especially in Nigeria because of teachers' inability to use effective modes of instruction. This is an indication that the effectiveness of such modes of instruction might depend on the ability of the teacher to use the appropriate mode of instruction such as peer assisted learning and students Engagement to boost the interest of students in mathematics. Nigerian students especially at secondary school level are not performing acceptably well in English and mathematics in both internal and external examinations. The findings have attested to the fact that learners performance in English and Mathematics at secondary school levels remain unsatisfactory. Results from researches have attributed the high failure rate in biology to a number of factors such as, inappropriate teaching methods, existence of abstract concepts, students' misconception of science, improper use of instructional materials, large class size, lack of well trained teachers, constant use of lecture method and over loaded curriculum.

However, some teachers are not aware of the significant suitable method due to inadequate knowledge or perhaps low professional training. Peer assisted learning strategy and students engagement are reported as effective in the teaching and learning of English and Mathematics at various part of the world. In a student's engagement lesson, students work together to attain group goals that may not be obtain by working alone or competitively (Adeduran, 2021). The experiences attained by learners through stud promote more positive attitudes toward the instructional experience than competitive or individualistic methodologies. Evidence reveals that, when students are engaged in learning among peers, they

performed extremely better than those in a non engaged learning class. Kulbir (2021) describe successful peer assisted learning tasks as intellectually demanding, creative, open-ended, and involve higher order thinking tasks. Therefore, the main thrust of the study about the effect of Peer assisted leaning strategy and student's engagement on academic performance in secondary schools in Sokoto Metropolis, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

1. The effect of peer assisted learning strategies on academic performance among senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis.
2. The effect of student engagement on academic performance among senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis.
3. The differential effect of peer assisted learning strategies on academic performance between male and female senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis.
4. The differential effect of engagement between student engagement on academic performance between male and female secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis.
5. The differential effect of peer assisted learning strategies and student engagement on academic performance among senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis.

Research Hypotheses

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of academic performances of students exposed to peer assisted learning strategy.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of academic performances of students exposed to student engagement strategy.

HO₃: There is no significant differential effect of peer assisted learning strategies of male and female students' academic performance of those taught using student engagement strategy.

HO₄: There is no significant differential effect of student engagement of male and female students' academic performance of those taught using peer assisted learning strategy.

HO₅: There is no significant differential effect in the academic performance of students taught using peer assisted learning strategy and those taught using students' engagement strategy.

Review of Literature

Many educational studies have explored the relative efficacy of peer assisted learning strategy and students engagement on academic performance of senior secondary school students. The library of academic literature is replete with findings from studies conducted on how peer assisted learning strategies enhanced academic achievement in English studies. Omwirhiren (2017) conducted a study on the effects of peer assisted learning on students' academic performance in Ghana. The population of the study comprises 367 Senior secondary school students with a sample of 45 students. The studies revealed that, students taught comprehension with peer assisted learning strategies, performed significantly better than their counterpart taught using the conventional teaching method. He further noted that when English is taught using student centered instructional strategies, learner will be motivated to achieve better grades in English. Udo (2016) conducted a study on the effect peer assisted learning strategies, student centered demonstration and expository on the performance of students in biology using 452 studets in Kenya. The result of the study shows that, peer assisted learning strategies enhanced academic performance over student centered demonstration and expository method of instruction. The significantly better effect of peer assisted learning over student-centered demonstration is explained in terms of the intrinsic motivation the learners have from their discoveries.

The observation with respect to peer assisted learning, student-centered demonstration and expository methods further affirm the relative effectiveness of students-centered instructional approaches on their academic performances. Adejo (2015) in her study on the effect of peer assisted learning strategies on academic performance in mathematics in New Delhi. The population of the study comprises of 567 students while the sample of the study were 234 students. The findings of the study revealed that, mathematics students taught using peer assisted learning performed significantly better than their counterparts taught using traditional teaching method. Hence the study concluded that the peer assisted

learning, produced students with significantly higher academic performance in mathematics. Further studies conducted by Omwirhiren and Lawal (2016) on the effectiveness of teaching methods reveal that that peer assisted learning, students engagement and inquiry method can be used for teaching and learning processes depending on the topic but peer assisted learning is most effective because it affords the students the opportunity to study on their own. The potential of Deeper learning beyond the traditional rote learning was observed in these activity-based methods. Furthermore, it facilitates the transfer of ownership of learning to the students while the teacher functions as a facilitator. The teacher builds from students' prior knowledge and encourages them to construct their own views of the mathematics concepts.

In a study conducted by Jack and Suleiman (2017) on the Effectiveness of peer assisted learning strategies on Senior Secondary Schools Students' Academic Achievement in Volumetric Analysis, using a population of 5567 and a sample of 345 students in south Africa. The findings shows that peer assisted learning had much more effect on students' academic achievement than the traditional teaching method. Peer assisted learning, allows educators to create a unique learning experience for students. Teachers who can incorporate instructional methods like peer assisted learning strategy into their classrooms help students build a strong foundation of knowledge through active participation.

A meta-analysis study on the effect of peer assisted learning strategy in Science Teaching, was conducted by Ben and Kain, (2016). A total of 35 different effect sizes from 35 experimental studies, comprising 2918 students were included in the meta-analysis. The results confirmed that peer assisted learning strategy have a positive effect on students' achievement The overall effect size value obtained from independent studies was calculated as 1.245 (% 95 CI, SE = .148) between confidence intervals 956 and 1.534 according to the random effects model. Among all effect sizes 32 had a positive effect whereas 3 of them had negative effect. A number of sub-group analyses (school level, type of publication, subject matter and duration) were conducted. The effect of peer assisted learning was not significant for school level, type of publication and duration. However, regarding the subject matter a significant difference was observed. The high effect size calculated in this meta-analysis implies that the guided inquiry method was a useful strategy that should be included in science curriculums.

A meta-analysis study to evaluate the effect of peer assisted learning strategy on academic achievement, and scientific process skills was carried out by Nikkita (2018). The result of the study shows that peer assisted learning had an effect on the students' academic achievement, attitude towards science and science process skills. By analyzing the data obtained from the articles and theses, a general evaluation was made about the effect of peer assisted on academic achievement, attitude toward science and science process skills. As a result of the study, the effect of the method applied for each dependent variable was found to favor the experimental group.

The investigations of Ajaja and Eravwoke (2019) was to determine the effects of peer assisted learning as an instructional strategy on physics students' performance. The study included two instructional groups (experimental and control groups).The samples of the study included six senior secondary schools, 112 science students, and 12 chemistry teachers. The instruments used for this study were: teacher's questionnaire on knowledge and use of learning cycle (KULC); and physics Achievement Test (PCAT). The data collected were analyzed with simple percentage, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and student t-test statistics. The major findings of the study included that only 30.43% physics teachers have the knowledge that peer assisted learning is an instructional method; all the physics teachers sampled have never used peer assisted learning strategy as an instructional method; Therefore, peer assisted learning strategy had a significant effect on students achievement in physics. Students taught using peer assisted learning significantly achieved better performance in physics Post-test than those taught with lecture method; the post-test scores of students in the peer assisted learning, increased over the period of experience; It was concluded that the method seems an appropriate instructional model that could be used to solve the problems of science teaching and learning since it facilitates learning. Zaitoun (2020) and Ahmed, (2021) opined that peer assisted learning strategies takes into account of Individual differences, introduce progress in knowledge and science as a way of research where the student follows the learning

from micro to macro, motivate student to use mental processes, and show attention to focus on the development of multi-thinking skills, based on thrill and excitement to attract attention, also depends on the explanation and interpretation, discussion and collaborative learning, and also depends on the detailed expansionist thinking, makes learning meaningful and helps edit understanding error, and finally provides the student with many different ways of evaluation.

METHODOLOGY

The research employed quasi experimental design of pre-test, post-test and control group in investigating effect of peer assisted learning strategies and student's engagement on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis. Pre-test post-test and control group will be use to determine the effectiveness of the techniques on academic performance of senior secondary school students by comparing pre-test, post-test and control group mean scores of English of the participants after treatment sessions. In line with this study, the researcher uses peer assisted learning strategies and students engagement to observe their effectiveness on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sokoto metropolis. The quasi-experimental design is graphically presented below:

Figure 3.1: Research Design Illustrated

EG => O1AP => X1 => O2AP

CG => O1AP => X2 => O2AP

Where:

EG = Experimental group exposed to peer assisted learning

CG = Control group exposed to students engagement strategies

O1AP = Academic performance before treatment (pre-test)

O2AP = Academic performance after treatment (post-test)

X1 = Treatment (peer assisted learning)

X2 = Treatment (students engagement strategy)

The variables of the study would be independent, dependent and moderating variables. The independent variables are the peer assisted learning strategy and student engagement while the dependent variable is the performance of students in English the moderating variables are the gender of students. The population of this study consists of all SS II sciences students across thirty-four (34) senior secondary schools in Sokoto metropolis. With a total population of eight thousand eight hundred and thirty-six (8,836) English students. According to Sokoto state ministry of Education as of (2022). Purposively sampling technique will be used to selected four (4) out the thirty-four (34). Two schools for two treatment groups and schools for two control groups for this study. Instrumentation is the process of selecting or developing measuring devices for gathering desired data. For the purposed of this study English Studies (ESPT) Performance Test (MPT). The instruments were designed by the researcher which contains 25 multiple choice items each used to measure academic performance. The researcher considers questions from WAEC and NECO appropriately because they have already been validated and standardized. Under this heading the researcher intended to use one research instrument (EMPT) and 2 lesson plans for peer assisted learning and student's engagement strategies. The face and content validity were used by the researcher, where the drafted English Performance Test (EPT) and was presented to experts in the Department of Educational Foundation, Faculty of Education and Extension Services. Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto, for their vetting and guidance, with the view of establishing a valid instrument for the study. The researcher relied on the assertion made by Kerlinger (2013) who believed that, validation by specialists and experts is an effective method for content validation of research instruments. The pilot testing conducted further strengthened the validity of the instrument.

The reliability of the English Performance Test (EPT) instrument was established using split-half method. The instrument was distributed to thirty experimental group (taught English using peer assisted learning) and control group (taught English using students engagement strategies) at Government Day Secondary School Tudun Wada. The scores of the instrument were totaled and split into odd and even numbers. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to correlate the scores and obtained

the index of 0.61. This is the reliability of the half of the instrument. The index was beefed up into using Prophecy formula to obtain the reliability index of 0.71 for the whole instrument. This is considered high enough for administration. Instrument was also established using split-half method. The instrument was distributed to thirty experimental group (taught English using peer assisted learning) and control group (taught English using students engagement strategies) at Government Day Secondary School Tudun Wada. The scores of the instruments were totaled and split into odd and even numbers. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to correlate the scores and obtained the index of 0.61. This is the reliability of the half of the instrument. The index was beefed up into using Prophecy formula to obtain the reliability index of 0.81 for the whole instrument. This is considered high enough for administration. The data collected in this study was subjected to statistical analyses using descriptive and inferential statistics to answer the research questions. Paired samples t-test was used in testing hypotheses one, two, and five (1, 2, & 5) while an independent samples t-test was used to test hypotheses three and four (3 & 4). All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The analyses was conducted using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 26).

RESULTS

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of academic performances of students exposed to peer assisted learning strategy.

This hypothesis was tested by subjecting the pre-test and post-test academic performance scores of students exposed to peer assisted learning strategy to a Paired Samples t-test analysis and the result was presented in table 4.3.1.

Table 1: Difference in the pre-test and post-test academic performance scores of students exposed to peer assisted learning strategy

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Pre-test	40	10.83	2.395	-14.208	.000	H ₀ Rejected
Post-test	40	27.00	7.633			

Result of table 1 indicates that significant academic performance difference that exists among students taught before (Mean = 10.83) and after (Mean = 27.00) using peer assisted learning strategy though negative was significant, $t(39) = -14.208$, $p = .000$. Thus, since the p -value is less than the .05 level of significance, H₀₁ which states that there is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of academic performances of students exposed to peer assisted learning strategy was rejected.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of academic performances of students exposed to student engagement strategy.

Table 2: Difference in the pre-test and post-test academic performance scores of students exposed to student engagement strategy

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Pre-test	40	10.80	2.441	-10.726	.000	H ₀ Rejected
Post-test	40	26.45	8.443			

Result of table 2 indicates that significant academic performance difference that exists among students taught before (Mean = 10.80) and after (Mean = 26.45) using student engagement strategy though negative was significant, $t(39) = -10.726$, $p = .000$. Thus, since the p -value is less than the .05 level of significance, H₀₂ which states that there is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of academic performances of students exposed to student engagement strategy was rejected.

H₀₃: There is no significant differential effect of peer assisted learning strategy of male and female students' academic performance of those taught using student engagement strategy.

Table 3: Difference in the effect of peer assisted learning strategy between Male and Female students taught using student engagement strategy

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Male	20	27.20	6.101	-.164	.871	H ₀ Accepted
Female	20	26.80	9.070			

Result of table 3 indicates that significant academic performance difference that exists between the male students (Mean = 27.20) and female students (Mean = 26.80) using students' engagement strategy was negative and not significant, $t(38) = -.164, p > .05$. Thus, since the p -value is more than the .05 level of significance, H₀₃ which states that there is no significant differential effect of peer assisted learning strategies of male and female students' academic performance of those taught using student engagement strategy was accepted.

H₀₄: There is no significant differential effect of student engagement of male and female students' academic performance of those taught using peer assisted learning strategy.

Table 4: Difference in the effect of student engagement between Male and Female students taught using student assisted learning strategy

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Male	20	29.80	6.453	-2.705	.010	H ₀ Rejected
Female	20	23.10	9.002			

Result of table 4 indicates that significant academic performance difference that exists between the male students (Mean = 29.80) and female students (Mean = 23.10) using student assisted learning strategy though negative was significant, $t(38) = -.164, p = .010$. Thus, since the p -value is less than the .05 level of significance, H₀₄ which states that there is no significant differential effect of student engagement of male and female students' academic performance of those taught using student assisted learning strategy was rejected.

H₀₅: There is no significant differential effect in the academic performance of students taught using peer assisted learning strategy and those taught using students' engagement strategy.

Table 5: Difference in academic performance of students taught using peer assisted learning strategy and those taught using students' engagement strategy

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Cal	p-Value	Decision
Peer Assisted Learning	40	27.00	7.633	.316	.754	H ₀ Accepted
Students' Engagement	40	26.45	8.443			

Result of table 5 indicates that significant difference does not exist between students taught using peer assisted learning strategy (Mean = 27.00) and those taught using students' engagement strategy (Mean = 26.45) and though positive is non-significant, $t(39) = .316, p > .05$. Thus, since the p -value is more than the .05 level of significance, H₀₅ which states that there is no significant differential effect in the academic performance of students taught using peer assisted learning strategy and those taught using students' engagement strategy was accepted.

Summary of Findings

The following are the major findings of the study:

1. Academic performances of students increase after being exposed to peer assisted learning strategy.
2. Academic performances of students increase after being exposed to students' engagement strategy.
3. Significant differential effect of peer assisted learning strategy is not significant among male and female students' academic performance taught using student engagement strategy.
4. Significant differential effect of student engagement exists in male and female students' academic performance taught using student engagement strategy.
5. Academic performance of students taught using peer assisted learning strategy does not differ significantly much from of those taught using students' engagement strategy.

DISCUSSION

Considering academic performance and students peer assisted learning strategy in secondary schools situation similar to that of the researcher, Patrick (2020) conducted a study comparing the effect of two teaching methods (peer assisted learning and students engagement) on recall of facts, understanding of content, and application of principles among gender. The sample for this study was very small, and it was not random. The findings of the study concluded that there was a differential effect on students' learning as measured by examination among these two methods. The female' mean scores for recalling and understanding were higher than males in the peer assisted learning than the students engagement, but for application the scores of males were higher in the peer assisted learning than the students engagement. Peer assisted learning strategies is a better method for retention of the content students engagement. However, the students' engagement method allows students to become active and creative. It was also found that the male students were superior in performance on examination than the female students. But, for retention and a higher level of thinking. The female students were superior.

Five different teaching methods was compared by Randall (2020). Two of them were peer assisted learning strategies and students' engagement. In the study, he indicated that peer assisted learning was an effective way of instruction because it involve collaboration of students. Also, he also stated that students engagement can be used to introduce a new subject and for making a summary at the end of a session. In the peer assisted learning method a teacher leads his/her class and steers the students in order to accomplish the objectives. Peer assisted learning involves thinking, and any student can participate. As the author stated, the peer assisted learning strategy leads to better learning and retention. However, this method is more time consuming than the lecture, and it is more adaptable to a small group of 25 students or less. Randall (2020) stated that the peer assisted learning strategy had some advantages such as: students learned better through discussion, the cooperation helped students raise questions and answer them, the students were free to give comments or not, and cooperative method had a positive effect upon the mental activity of the students. Moreover, there were some disadvantages such as: peer assisted learning need a lengthy time, some students may never participate, and there were problems in evaluating the students.

To investigate the effect of gender and mathematics ability on academic performance of students in physics using peer assisted learning strategies students engagement, Udousoro (2019), carried out a study with a population comprises of 500 senior secondary physics students selected from two secondary schools in Uyo. The sample of the study involves 100 senior secondary physics students selected from the target population. The outcome shows that gender does not have significant effect on student's engagement in physics. Female students taught physics performed significantly higher and better than their male counterparts taught physics using peer assisted learning strategies.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings in this research indicated that there is no significant relationship existing between Peer assisted learning strategies and student's engagement Strategies for academic performance in Senior Secondary Schools in the Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto State- Nigeria. This indicates that if teachers are

given adequate factors to boost their attitude like motivation, involvement in decisions and goal planning, commendation at improved performance and good working environment, It will help in the formation of personality which will enhance students learning. It can therefore be concluded that the factors that causes teachers' negative attitude at work are lack of concern from the school management, good working environment, absence of motivation and involvement of teachers in decision making. Teaching and Learning can be properly succeed, grow or even survive when adequately address issues affecting Teachers', students related factors in Senior Secondary Schools within the Sokoto Metropolis of Sokoto Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. The research supports the importance of building positive personality relationships between Secondary Schools Teachers and Students, which should in turn serve as motivation to the peer assisted learning strategies for engaging students academic performance. The findings of this study also indicated that these relationships are being nurtured in the Secondary Schools investigated where a critical gap still exists between Female and Male Students especially in the areas of achievement motivation.
- ii. Female Students should be giving equal attention with their male counterparts by the teachers regardless of race, gender disposition and economic status so as to address gender related factors established in the research. From the results findings, it revealed that female students are neglected or lagging behind in terms of attention by most Secondary Schools female teachers in some of the Secondary Schools within Sokoto Metropolis by virtue of gender and feminine roles. It is also recommended that Teachers in Secondary Schools should serve as role models for the Students' to emulate regardless of gender or race, set realistic academic performance goals and help students achieve them by encouraging them to set their own reasonable goals irrespective of gender disposition or bias.
- iii. To enhance Peer assisted learning strategies in our Secondary Schools that will engage students academic performance, there is need for training and retraining of Secondary Schools Teachers in the Sokoto Metropolis. This would improve the academic status of teachers acquainted with the dynamic nature of the peer group teaching strategies, thematic, content, methodologies and pedagogical skills appropriate in the delivery of comprehensive lessons.
- iv. Appointment of Secondary Schools teachers should emphasize on Teachers with minimum qualification and well trained in Education rather than playing politics of sons and daughters of the soil in the appointment and posting of Teachers.
- v. There should be a policy statement banning the recruitment or appointment of teaching staff to teach in Secondary Schools without a satisfied morale and having acquired a professional training in Education. This would go a long way in engaging learners to show interest in their choice of subjects and career.
- vi. A refresher training should be organized among the teachers with different qualifications at regular intervals so as to update their knowledge and familiarize with the dynamic nature of peer learning strategies in Secondary Schools particularly content, themes, methodologies as well as in the areas of pedagogical teaching skills and tools used in the evaluation of the learning outcomes in the Secondary Schools covered by the study.
- vii. There is need for the Teachers to spend most time with the Students and should be able to motivate them as a result of using varieties of teaching methods taking into considerations; individual differences, the slow and fast learners, gifted and talented students, convergers, divergers as well as the scanners. This is to make students interested in the subject matter of the lessons having encouraged by the good sense of humour, warmth reception, social interactions and enthusiasm.
- viii. There should be remuneration of service for the secondary schools teachers in the Study area so as to enhance their efficiency and effectiveness in teaching and learning. From the findings in this

research, it was discovered that the morale of Teachers in the secondary schools was at a very lowest ebb and this had great influenced in the development of positive attitude to work which in turn affects Students motivation for academic performance. When Teachers are motivated with a well paid Salary and arrears, promoted as at when due, enjoyed allowances and other entitlements for his/her services, can create a lively personality and energetic classroom whereby Students' will be very satisfied and motivated.

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